

Evaluating the health of Iranian contemporary family and its changes

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Abstract:

Introduction: Nutritional health of family and planning to achieve healthy diet are one of the most important concerns of contemporary humans. With regard to the employment of men and women in outdoors and easy access to fast foods, the use of healthy food has changed. The aim of this study was to investigate the nutritional health of Iranian families and its changes.

Methods: In this study, 120 persons in Tehran, aged from 30 to 60 were selected using available sampling method. They were still using fast food, despite being aware of the losses of using it. Cronbach's alpha of questionnaire was 0.5. Data were analyzed using SPSS 16 in two stages using quasi-experimental method.

Findings: The status of prepared meals in the food program of different groups showed that employed men (58.33%) more than twice as many employed women (28%), employed single persons more than married ones, employed married women more than housewives consumed fast foods. Since the organization of a family nutrition in our culture is the responsibility of women, comparison of percentages showed that although married housewives less than any other group used fast food, in general, nearly half of the participants used ready meals despite being familiar with the losses of using fast foods.

Conclusion: The present study has indicated that women are less likely than men to change food habits. The nutritional health of Iranian families is threatened and subjected to McDonaldization so that the malicious propaganda also has an impact on persuading people to eat fast foods that need to be fought. Therefore, this study explains the need for healthy policies in this regard.

Keywords: Family, Women, Health, Fast food (ready meal)